

C-reactive protein to albumin ratio, albumin to globulin ratio and platelet to lymphocyte ratio in patients with spondyloarthritis

Spondiloartropatili hastalarda C reaktif protein albümin oranı, albümin globülin oranı, platelet lenfosit oranı

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Abstract

Aim: The C-reactive protein (CRP) to albumin ratio (CAR) has been reported as a novel inflammatory marker to assess inflammation. Serum globulin increases in inflammation. In this study, it was aimed to evaluate relation between CAR, albumin to globulin ratio (AGR), platelet to lymphocyte ratio (PLR) and disease activity in patients with axial spondyloarthritis (AxSpA).

Method: Seventy-five patients with axial SpA and seventy-five healthy controls were evaluated retrospectively. CRP, albumin, globulin, leukocyte, lymphocyte, and platelet from the patients and controls were recorded. CAR, AGR and PLR were calculated. Disease activity was evaluated by the BASDAI and ASDAS.

Results: The mean age was 38.2±10.39 years in patients with AxSpA and 35.45±8.96 years in controls. The CAR was 0.153±0.2 in AxSpA patients and 0.03±0.02 in controls (p<0.05). The CAR was 0.0972±0.16 in patients who had low disease activity and 0.213±0.275 in patients with high disease activity. The patients with high disease activity had higher CAR than patients with low disease activity (p<0.05). There was a statistically significant positive correlation between CAR and BASDAI and ASDAS respectively (rho 327, p<0.05, rho 0.523, p<0.05). The AGR was lower in AxSpA patients (p<0.05). There was a negative correlation between AGR and BASDAI but it was not significant (rho - 0.044, p>0.05). There was significant correlation between PLR and BASDAI and ASDAS (rho 236, p<0.05 and rho 314, p<0.05 respectively).

Conclusion: The CAR and PLR are an important markers for evaluating disease activity in patients with AxSpA. AGR may be a promising marker for assessing disease activity in AxSpA.

Özet

Amaç: C-reaktif protein (CRP) albümin oranı (CAO), inflamasyonu değerlendirmek için yeni bir inflamatuvar belirteç olarak belirtilmiştir. Serum globulini inflamasyonda artar. Bu çalışmada aksiyal spondiloartritli (AxSpA) hastalarda hastalık aktivitesini ile (CAO), albümin globulin oranı (AGO) ve platelet lenfosit oranı (PLO) arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemek amaçlandı.

Yöntem: Yetmiş beş aksiyel SpA'lı hasta ve yetmiş beş sağlıklı kontrol retrospektif olarak değerlendirildi. Hasta ve kontrollerin CRP, albumin, globulin, lökosit, lenfosit, nötrofil ve platelet değerleri kaydedildi. CAO, AGO ve PLO hesaplandı. Hastalık aktivitesi BASDAI ve ASDAS ile değerlendirildi.

Bulgular: Ortalama yaş AxSpA hastalarında 38.2±10.39 yıl ve kontrollerde 35.45±8.96 yıl idi. CAO AxSpA hastalarında 0.153±0.2 ve kontrollerde 0.03±0.02 idi (p<0.05). CAO düşük hastalık aktiviteli hastalarda 0.0972±0.16, yüksek hastalık aktiviteli hastalarda 0.213±0.275 idi. Yüksek hastalık aktivitesi olan hastalar, düşük hastalık aktivitesi olan hastalardan daha yüksek CAO'ya sahipti (p<0.05). Sırasıyla CAO ile ve BASDAI ve ASDAS arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı pozitif korelasyon vardı (rho 327, p<0.05 ve rho 0.523, p<0.05). AxSpA hastalarında AGO daha düşüktü (p<0.05). AGO ile BASDAI arasında negatif korelasyon vardı ancak anlamlı değildi (rho - 0.044, p>0.05). PLO ile BASDAI ve ASDAS arasında anlamlı bir ilişki vardı (rho 236, p<0.05, rho 314, p<0.05 sırasıyla).

Sonuç: CAO ve PLO, AxSpA'lı hastalarda hastalık aktivitesini değerlendirmek için önemli bir belirteçtir. AGO, AxSpA'daki hastalık aktivitesini değerlendirmek için umut verici bir belirteç olabilir.

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Introduction

Axial spondyloarthritis (SpA) is a chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease that affects axial skeleton, sacroiliac joint, entheses and peripheral joints. Axial SpA includes both ankylosing spondylitis (AS) and non-radiographic axial SpA (1). Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP) are commonly used as inflammatory indicators in AS but it has been reported that the CRP and ESR increase in up to 70% of patient with AS who have an active disease (2,3).

Albumin is a plasma protein which maintains colloid pressure and transports fatty acids and drug metabolites. Plasma albumin concentration is controlled by albumin synthesis rate, fractional catabolic rate and loss of exogenous albumin. The albumin synthesis rate is affected by inflammation and nutrition. Albumin is a negative acute phase protein (4,5)

The CRP to albumin ratio (CAR) has been reported as a novel inflammatory marker to assess inflammation, and it has been accepted as a prognostic indicator for some types of cancer such as colorectal cancers (6). The CAR has also been evaluated as an indicator of inflammation in some rheumatological diseases and it has been reported that CAR is associated with disease activity in patients with RA (7). Globulin has been indicated as a marker involved in inflammation and infection. The decreased albumin to globulin ratio (AGR) and elevated serum globulin levels were found to be related with infection and multiple myeloma and serum globulin increases in inflammation (7-10). Although albumin, globulin, CAR and AGR are an important biomarker for inflammation, there exists are only a few studies which have examined CAR and AGR in Ax SpA.

The aim of this study was to investigate whether CAR and AGR could be used to evaluate the disease activity in patients with AxSpA.

Material method

In this study, seventy-five patients with axial SpA according to ASAS classification criteria and seventy-five age and gender-matched healthy controls were evaluated retrospectively. Subjects with a diagnosis of acute and chronic infection, malignancy, chronic liver disease, and kidney failure that may affect albumin, globulin levels and blood parameters, were all excluded.

Parameters such as age, gender, disease duration, ESR, CRP, albumin, globulin, leukocyte, lymphocyte, neutrophil, and thrombocyte from the patients and controls were recorded from medical patient records. The demographic characteristics of subjects and disease-related characteristics of Ax SpA patients were recorded from hospital electronic records. CAR, AGR, neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and platelet to

lymphocyte ratio (LPR) were calculated by dividing CRP into albumin, albumin into globulin, neutrophil into lymphocyte, and platelet into lymphocyte, respectively. Disease activity was evaluated by using the Bath ankylosing spondylitis disease activity index (BASDAI) (11) and the Ankylosing spondylitis disease activity score (ASDAS) (12). ASDAS evaluates back pain, morning stiffness, joint involvement, patient general assessment in combination with laboratory parameters. The BASDAI scores of less than four were accepted as an inactive disease and scores of four or above were accepted as an active disease. Functionality was appraised by using the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Functional Index (BASFI) (13).

Statistics The continuous variables were showed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The Student t-test was used to compare the continuous variables. The Pearson's correlation test was used to study the relationship between parameters. The IBM-SPSS16 was used in all statistical analyses and a p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. This study was performed according to the Declaration of Helsinki and permission for the study was obtained from the Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University Faculty of Medicine Ethics Committee, decision number 12-14 on 07/07/2021.

Results

The mean age was 38.2 ± 10.39 years in patients with AxSpA and 35.45 ± 8.96 years in controls, respectively ($p > 0.05$). The features of the subjects are reported in Table 1. The 48% of patients had active disease as measured by BASDAI. The CAR was 0.153 ± 0.2 in AxSpA patients and 0.03 ± 0.02 in controls and it was higher in AxSpA patients compared to controls ($p < 0.05$). The AGR was 1.52 ± 0.24 in an AxSpA patients. The CAR was 0.0972 ± 0.16 in patients who had low disease activity and 0.213 ± 0.275 in patients with high disease activity and those with high disease activity had higher CAR than patients with low disease activity ($p < 0.05$). There was a statistically significant positive correlation between CAR and BASDAI and ASDAS, respectively ($\rho = 0.327$, $p < 0.05$, $\rho = 0.523$, $p < 0.05$) (Table 2). The AGR was lower in AxSpA patients ($p < 0.05$) and there was a negative correlation between AGR and BASDAI but it was not significant ($\rho = -0.044$, $p > 0.05$). There was no difference in terms of the NLR between AxSpA patients and healthy controls ($p > 0.05$). The NLR was positively correlated with BASDAI and ASDAS, but it was not significant ($\rho = 0.046$, $p > 0.05$ and $\rho = 0.081$, $p > 0.05$ respectively).

There was no difference in PLR between AxSpA patients and controls but PLR was significantly correlated with BASDAI and ASDAS ($\rho = 0.236$, $p < 0.05$ and $\rho = 0.314$, $p < 0.05$ respectively). There was a significant positive correlation between CRP and PLR in AxSpA ($\rho = 0.377$, $p < 0.05$) and the PLR was positively correlated with CAR ($\rho = 0.354$, $p < 0.05$). The CRP was positively correlated with NLR though it was not significant ($\rho = 0.07$, $p > 0.05$).

Discussion

This study was performed to compare the albumin, globulin, CAR, AGR, PLR and NLR in patients with AxSpA and healthy controls and to investigate the relationship between these parameters and disease activity. It was observed that CAR was higher and AGR was lower in AxSpA patients compared to controls. There was a positive correlation between CAR and disease activity.

Furthermore, it was found that albumin was lower and the CRP was higher in patients with AxSpA. He et al. investigated CAR in patients who had RA, SLE and healthy controls and they reported that CAR was higher in patients with a diagnosis of RA (14). In my study, CAR was higher in AxSpA patient and also CAR was higher in patients with an active disease compared to patients with an inactive disease. Similar to this result, Pamukçu et al. found that CAR was higher in patients with an active disease and there was a positive correlation between CAR and disease activity, however they evaluated disease activity only using the BASDAI (15). In my study disease activity was assessed using both the BASDAI and the ASDAS. Zhong et al. reported that CAR was higher in patients and also in patients with high disease activity (16). Therefore, my study differentiates itself from others in that disease activity was evaluated using the BASDAI and the ASDAS and there was a significant correlation between CAR and BASDAI and ASDAS.

AGR has been investigated in a wide variety of diseases to date. Yongyu et al compared globulin and AGR in patients who had undergone a revision of a total joint arthroplasty. They found that higher globulin and lower AGR were related to periprosthetic joint infection (17). A meta-analysis showed that low pretreatment AGR was related poor prognosis in cancers (18). Sütçüoğlu et al. showed that low AGR was related with increased risk of mortality in febrile neutropenia (19).

In this study, globulin was higher and AGR was lower in patients with AxSpA compared to controls. Although it was not significant, there was a negative correlation between BASDAI and AGR. Similar to this result Wang et al. reported that AGR was higher in patient with AxSpA, but they did not investigate the correlation between AGR and disease activity score (20). This suggests that there is a need for studies evaluating the relationship of AGR in patients with AxSpA.

In this study, NLR was not different in patients and controls but there was a positive correlation between disease activity and NLR. Gökmen et al. reported that NLR was higher in AS patients than controls and NLR was significantly correlated with CRP (21). Similar to these findings, Mercan et al. found that NLR was higher in AS patients, though they did not find any correlation between NLR and BASDAI (22). These results show that the significance of NLR in patients with Ax SpA

remains unclear.

In this study, PLR was positively correlated with CRP, BASDAI and ASDAS. Similar to this result a meta-analysis showed that CRP was positively correlated with PLR. This result suggests that PLR can be used to evaluate disease activity in AxSpA (23).

CAR and PLR are important markers for evaluating disease activity in patients with AxSpA. AGR for its part may be a promising marker for assessing disease activity in AxSpA, although there is a need for large samples studies evaluating the relationship of AGR in patients with AxSpA.

Table 1: The characteristics of patients and healthy controls.

	AxSpA	Healthy controls	P value
Age	38.2±10.39	35.45±8.96	p>0.05
ESR	12.99±11.48	6.1±5.3	p<0.05
CRP	0.68±1.02	0.167±0.128	p<0.05
Albumin	4.5±0.33	4.6±0.27	p<0.05
Globulin	3.01±0.4	2.8±0.4	p<0.05
CAR	0.153±0.2	0.03±0.02	p<0.05
AGR	1.52±0.24	1.68±0.25	p<0.05
NLR	1.92±0.95	1.98±0.64	p>0.05
PLR	128.15±46.10	135.45±41.92	p>0.05
Leukocyte	7390.66±1977.41	6508.22±1501.62	p<0.05
Lymphocyte	2306.19±704.32	2070.54±519.48	p<0.05
Neutrophil	4185.04±1715.7	3938.6±1281.09	p>0.05
Platelet	273405.4±59531.7	264706.6±56259.4	p>0.05

Table 2: The correlations between CAR, AGR, PLR and parameters in AxSpA patients.

	CAR	AGR	PLR
CRP	(rho 0.998, p<0.05)	(rho -0.155, p>0.05)	(rho 0.377, p<0.05)
ESR	(rho 0.16, p>0.05)	(rho -0.430, p<0.05)	(rho 0.199, p>0.05)
BASDAI	(rho 0.327, p<0.05)	(rho -0.04, p>0.05)	(rho 0.236, p<0.05)
ASDAS	(rho 0.523, p<0.05)	(rho 0.08, p>0.05)	(rho 0.314, p<0.05)
NLR	(rho 0.06, p>0.05)	(rho 0.155, p>0.05)	(rho 0.273, p<0.05)

REFERENCES

- Bb Deodhar A, Mease PJ, Reveille JD, Curtis JR, Chen S, Malhotra K, Pangan AL. Arthritis Rheumatol. Frequency of Axial Spondyloarthritis Diagnosis Among Patients Seen by US Rheumatologists for Evaluation of Chronic Back Pain. 2016 Jul;68(7):1669-76. doi: 10.1002/art.39612.
- Benhamou M, Gossec L, Dougados M. Clinical relevance of C-reactive protein in ankylosing spondylitis and evaluation of the NSAIDs/coxibs' treatment effect on C-reactive protein. Rheumatology (Oxford). 2010 Mar;49(3):536-41. doi: 10.1093/rheumatology/kep393.
- J Sieper, J Braun, M Rudwaleit, A Boonen, A Zink. Ankylosing spondylitis: an overview. Extended report. Ann Rheum Dis 2002;61(Suppl III):iii8-iii18
- Don BR, Kaysen G. Serum albumin: relationship to inflammation and nutrition Semin Dial. 2004 Nov-Dec;17(6):432-7. doi: 10.1111/j.0894-0959.2004.17603.x.
- Zhong Z, Huang Y, Liu Y, Chen J, Liu M, Huang Q, Zheng S, Guo X, Deng W, Li T. Correlation between C-Reactive Protein to Albumin Ratio and Disease Activity in Patients with Axial Spondyloarthritis. Dis Markers. 2021 Jun 12;2021:6642486. doi: 10.1155/2021/6642486. eCollection 2021.
- M. Ishizuka, H. Nagata, K. Takagi, Y. Iwasaki, N. Shibuya, and K. Kubota, "Clinical significance of the C-reactive protein to albumin ratio for survival after surgery for colorectal cancer," Annals of Surgical Oncology, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 900-907, 2016.
- Ye Y, Chen W, Gu M, Xian G, Pan B, Zheng L, Zhang Z, Sheng P. Serum globulin and albumin to globulin ratio as potential diagnostic biomarkers for periprosthetic joint infection: a retrospective review. J Orthop Surg Res. 2020 Oct 7;15(1):459. doi: 10.1186/s13018-020-01959-1.
- Cai Y, Zhao Y, Dai Q, Xu M, Xu X, Xia W. Prognostic value of the albumin-globulin ratio and albumin-globulin score in patients with multiple myeloma. J Int Med Res. 2021 Mar;49(3):30006521997736. doi: 10.1177/030006521997736.
- Li K, Fu W, Bo Y, Zhu Y. Effect of albumin-globulin score and albumin to globulin ratio on survival in patients with heart failure: a retrospective cohort study in China. BMJ Open. 2018;8(7):e22960.
- Guo HW, Yuan TZ, Chen JX, Zheng Y. Prognostic value of pretreatment albumin/globulin ratio in digestive system cancers: a meta-analysis. PLoS One. 2018;13(1):e189839.

11. Garrett S, Jenkinson T, Kennedy LG, Whitlock H, Gaisford P, Calin A. A new approach to defining disease status in ankylosing spondylitis: the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Index. *J Rheumatol* 1994;21:2286-91, PMID: 7699630
12. Lukas C, Landewé R, Sieper J, Dougados M, Davis J, Braun J et al. Development of an ASAS-endorsed disease activity score (ASDAS) in patients with ankylosing spondylitis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2009;68:18-24, DOI: 10.1136/ard.2008.094870
13. Yanik B, Gürsel YK, Kutlay S, Ay S, Elhan AH. Adaptation of the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Functional Index to the Turkish population, its reliability and validity: functional assessment in AS. *Clin Rheumatol* 2005;24:41-7, DOI: 10.1007/s10067-004-0968-6
14. He Y, Tang J, Wu B, Yang B, Ou Q, Lin J. Correlation between albumin to fibrinogen ratio, C-reactive protein to albumin ratio and Th17 cells in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2020 Jan;500:149-154. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2019.10.009
15. Pamuku M, Duran TI. Could C-Reactive Protein/Albumin Ratio be an Indicator of Activation in Axial Spondyloarthritis? *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2021 May;30(5):537-541. doi: 10.29271/jcpsp.2021.05.537. PMID: 34027865
16. Zhong Z, Huang Y, Liu Y, Chen J, Liu M, Huang Q, Zheng S, Guo X, Deng W, Li T. Correlation between C-Reactive Protein to Albumin Ratio and Disease Activity in Patients with Axial Spondyloarthritis. *Dis Markers*. 2021 Jun 12;2021:6642486. doi: 10.1155/2021/6642486
17. Ye Y, Chen W, Gu M, Xian G, Pan B, Zheng L, Zhang Z, Sheng P. Serum globulin and albumin to globulin ratio as potential diagnostic biomarkers for periprosthetic joint infection: a retrospective review. *J Orthop Surg Res*. 2020 Oct 7;15(1):459. doi: 10.1186/s13018-020-01959-1.
18. Lv GY, An L, Sun XD, Hu YL, Sun DW. Pretreatment albumin to globulin ratio can serve as a prognostic marker in human cancers: a meta-analysis. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2018 Jan;476:81-91. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2017.11.019. Epub 2017 Nov 21
19. Sütçüoğlu O, Akdoğan O, Gürler F, Kurt İnci B, Özdemir N, Özet A, Yazıcı O. The role of serum albumin/globulin ratio in combination with prognostic risk indexes of febrile neutropenia. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2021 Jul;75(7):e14185. doi: 10.1111/ijcp.14185.
20. Wang J, Su J, Yuan Y, Jin X, Shen B, Lu G. BMC Musculoskelet Disord. The role of lymphocyte-monocyte ratio on axial spondyloarthritis diagnosis and sacroiliitis staging. 2021 Jan 16;22(1):86. doi: 10.1186/s12891-021-03973-8.
21. Gökmen F, Akbal A, Reşorlu H, Gökmen E, Güven M, Aras AB, Erbağ G, Kömürçü E, Akbal E, Coşar M. Neutrophil-Lymphocyte Ratio Connected to Treatment Options and Inflammation Markers of Ankylosing Spondylitis. *J Clin Lab Anal*. 2015 Jul;29(4):294-8. doi: 10.1002/jcla.21768.
22. Mercan R, Bitik B, Tufan A, Bozbulut UB, Atas N, Öztürk MA, Haznedaroğlu S, Goker B. The Association Between Neutrophil/Lymphocyte Ratio and Disease Activity in Rheumatoid Arthritis and Ankylosing Spondylitis. *J Clin Lab Anal*. 2016 Sep;30(5):597-601. doi: 10.1002/jcla.21908.
23. Song GG, Lee YH. Red cell distribution width, platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio, and mean platelet volume in ankylosing spondylitis and their correlations with inflammation: A meta-analysis. *Mod Rheumatol*. 2020 Sep;30(5):894-899. doi: 10.1080/14397595.2019.1645373.